

Project¹ Number: 660067

Project Acronym: **COLD μ WAVE**

Project title: Energy Innovative Food Process For The Production Of High Quality Frozen Food

Report on ice crystal properties and vegetable microstructure after microwave assisted freezing

¹ The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation